

Assessing the effects of human capital composition, innovation portfolio and size on manufacturing firm performance

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Abstract

Purpose – This paper aims to focus on the effects of human capital composition, innovation portfolio and size on manufacturing firms' performance. Moreover, it seeks to empirically identify the levels of education that are significant in labour productivity.

Design/methodology/approach – The resource-based view (RBV) theory is applied using data gathered from the National Innovation Survey in the Manufacturing Industries of Peru. Using the ordinary least squares method on a sample of 584 Peruvian manufacturing firms, the effects on firm performance of two subsamples according to innovation portfolio and firm size are determined.

Findings – The direct effects of human capital composition on productivity show that the higher the workers' educational level, the higher the productivity. However, if this relationship is analysed in terms of the innovation portfolio, the authors find that labour productivity in companies with product–service innovation is greater (i.e. more significant) than in traditional manufacturing firms with only product innovations. Similarly, if this relationship is compared in terms of company, the authors find that large companies are more significant than small and medium-sized enterprises.

Practical implications – The study furthers the understanding of how the relationship between human capital composition, innovation portfolio and size of manufacturing firms positively affects labour productivity. Hence, it can help managers to craft their innovation portfolio according to the educational level of their human capital. This could require that not only human resource management innovates, but also that strategic partnerships be developed with educational establishments to boost training towards product–service innovation.

Originality/value – This study's results provide confirmation that the configuration of human resources, innovation portfolio and size plays a significant role on manufacturing firms' performance, particularly in the context of developing countries.

Keywords: Manufacturing strategy, Human capital, Labour productivity, Product–service innovation, Size

1. Introduction

In recent years, there has been an increase in empirical and theoretical work that addresses the role of innovation as one of the main sources of firm growth and productivity (Audretsch *et al.*, 2014). Competitive advantage lies in part with the firm's capacity to innovate, evaluate and exploit internal and external knowledge (Cohen and Levinthal, 1990). Studies in the field of management have focused on various internal characteristics of firms that affect their innovation behaviour, such as those related to intellectual capital (Subramaniam and Youndt, 2005), chief executive officer characteristics (Lin *et al.*, 2011) and human capital (Sun *et al.*, 2020). Hence, firm-specific human capital has been viewed as critical to fostering innovation and greater productivity. According to the resource-based view (RBV) theory, human capital is viewed as a critical resource (Barney and Wright, 1998) and provides a competitive advantage for firms in terms of skills, expertise and their willingness to work (Hewitt-Dundas, 2006). This research undertakes an evaluation of the workforce in terms of high, medium-high and medium-low levels of education, namely, *human capital composition* on firm's performance. In turn, it examines the effects of innovation portfolio and firm size upon this relationship and, in this context, poses three central research questions. Firstly, does human capital composition exert any effect in firm's labour productivity? Secondly, does human capital composition's effect on labour productivity relate to firm's innovation portfolio? And thirdly, does human capital composition's effect on labour productivity relate to firm's size?

Product–service innovation refers to the current debate on how manufacturing is moving from a product-based business model to a service-based business (Vendrell-Herrero *et al.*, 2020). This suggests a cross-fertilization of service practices and strategies towards manufacturing to create a product–service system (Bustinza *et al.*, 2017). The implementation of services in the manufacturing industry is an increasingly relevant topic, not only within European boundaries (Vendrell-Herrero and Bustinza, 2020). A consolidated academic community currently focuses on how these business models are deployed (Bustinza *et al.*, 2017) and what drivers and bottlenecks enable and hinder successful implementation of product–service innovation (Bustinza *et al.*, 2018). Under these business models, production firms attempt to enhance product features and capabilities, as well as consumer satisfaction, and to increase product differentiation by including services that support product capabilities during the product's entire life cycle in their business portfolio (Vendrell-Herrero and Bustinza, 2020). Therefore, a focus on the internal resources (human capital) and innovation portfolio of firms is a timely one.

On the other hand, many studies have focused on efforts to identify tangible internal and external conditions and attitudes towards innovation related to the individual person, for example, finding a positive significance to employees' qualifications and firm size in terms of their attitude to innovation (Coronado *et al.*, 2008), insofar as diversity in nationality and educational attainment in the workforce relates positively to firms' probability to engage in product innovation (McGuirk and Jordan, 2012). To date, however, there has been limited empirical research into whether levels of education contribute to productivity in the innovation portfolio, and this differs between small and larger-sized firms in developing country contexts.

Against this backdrop, the aim of this research is to measure the relationship between human capital composition and labour productivity according to firms' innovation portfolio and size in the context of Latin America. Some authors state that this region serves as a "natural laboratory" for testing existing theories originating from the USA and Europe (Aguinis *et al.*, 2020), for instance, using Latin America as a laboratory to better understand the relationship between inward foreign direct investment and outward foreign direct investment, and also examining the moderating effect of trade openness on that relationship (Reyes *et al.*, 2019). Meanwhile, Latin American multinationals were analysed and

suggestions were provided for using these firms as a laboratory for extending existing theories and multinational models (Cuervo-Cazurra, 2016). Latin America is a region of paradoxes (Cuervo-Cazurra and Dau, 2009; Vassolo *et al.*, 2011), and it is precisely these unique conditions that allow researchers to test theories, challenge implicit assumptions and research into new phenomena (Aguinis and Joo, 2014). However, the region remains largely underexplored in terms of management research (Nicholls-Nixon *et al.*, 2011). One of these opportunities is precisely the differential relevance of workers' skills. The economic growth experienced in Latin America combined with a brain drain process gives rise to a lack of qualified workers in the region (Aguinis *et al.*, 2020), and so it is much less common to hire graduates than in other regions of the world where the workforce tends to be over qualified. New evidence shows that a major obstacle faced by many firms in the region is the lack of adequate skills or high-level of education among the labour force. Thus, one of the most important challenges faced by Latin American economies is to increase the productivity of their workforces, as firms' demand for skills is associated with innovation (González-Velosa *et al.*, 2016), and in fact, the lack of skilled labour is seen as a constraint to innovation in small and medium-sized enterprises (SMEs) (Feldens *et al.*, 2012). Despite their importance, little is known about these issues (González-Velosa *et al.*, 2016), and so the aim of this study is to gain insight into this.

Our study focuses on the context of an emerging economy in Latin America, namely, Peru. Over the past decade, Peru has evidenced average GDP growth and shown macroeconomic strength. According to the World Bank (2015), Peru ranks second in the "best countries to do business within Latin America and the Caribbean". One of the primary reasons for choosing the manufacturing industry in Peru is its major relevance in terms of job creation. Approximately, 510,000 jobs were created by Peruvian manufacturing firms in 2016, out of 17% of the country's total (MINTRA, 2017), although one of the main reasons for the decline in share of the manufacturing industry in GDP from 17% in 2000 to 14% in 2015 (World Bank, 2017) may be because of low levels of labour productivity and external factors such as the price of minerals that had affected such manufacturing growth in Peru over the previous years. On the other hand, although innovation efforts in Peru have increased in recent years, e.g. research and development (R&D) spending per capita increase from \$4.77 in 2011 to \$7.12 in 2015 (RICYT, 2017), workers' skills are still scarce in these companies (Seclen-Luna *et al.*, 2020). The empirical analysis is based on a large firm-level data set extracted from the National Innovation Survey in the Manufacturing Industries of Peru (ENIIM, as its acronym is known in Spanish), with econometric regressions being used on a sample of 584 Peruvian manufacturing firms. The results show that the higher the worker's educational level, the higher the productivity, and in companies with product-service innovation, productivity is greater than traditional manufacturing firms that are engaged only in product innovations. Large companies also have a more significant relationship between human capital and labour productivity than SMEs.

The paper is structured as follows: Section 2 introduces the literature review and positioning of the study and this leads on to the research hypotheses. Section 3 details the database and tests the hypotheses proposed. The empirical results are provided in the Section 4. Lastly, Section 5 provides some brief conclusions, limitations and suggestions for future research.

2. Literature review and positioning of the study

The RBV theory posits that the sustainable competitive advantage and long-term positive performance of firms depends largely on valuable, rare, inimitable and organised (VRIO) internal assets (i.e. resources) that are accessible to, or controlled by, a firm (Newbert, 2008). Of these, human capital is especially critical (Barney and Wright, 1998; Wright *et al.*, 2001;

Roxas *et al.*, 2017). Following the RBV, human capital, such as the skills, knowledge, experience and formal educational training of a firm's workers, is considered essential internal capital that can lead to firms' competitive advantage and performance gains (Lafuente and Rabetino, 2011; Lin and Wu, 2014; Chowdhury *et al.*, 2014; Chowhan, 2016). In this study, human capital composition in terms of level of education (i.e. high-level education, medium-high level education and medium-low level education) is considered a strategic asset that can affect performance outcomes and labour productivity in manufacturing firms. This assertion is based on previous works that assess the role of human capital in terms of manufacturing performance (Corvers, 1997; Arvanitis and Loukis, 2009; Buller and McEvoy, 2012), hence, we build on the RBV as a backdrop for analysing the internal composition of knowledge resources, namely, the pool of education within a firm, which refers to the VRIO organisational resources capable of attaining competitive advantages and contributing to performance benefits.

A firm's competitive edge, however, lies in part in its capacity to innovate, evaluate and exploit internal knowledge (Cohen and Levinthal, 1990). In this vein, highly skilled/knowledgeable workers (i.e. more highly educated ones) are reported to be significantly more likely to develop new and innovative ideas (Amabile, 1988). Hence, organisational knowledge can increase a firm's innovation because of the production of new products/services, processes or methods, usually involving combining and applying all existing knowledge assets within that firm (Sorenson and Fleming, 2004). Therefore, human capital, in terms of knowledge embodied in an organisation's members, is identified as being a crucial driver for innovation and business performance in manufacturing firms (Sun *et al.*, 2020). As previously stated, the study at hand posits that human capital (in its different levels of education) may have an effect on a manufacturing firm's performance, although we argue that to some extent, this may be associated with its innovation portfolio (Ismail, 2018). In particular, we focus on manufacturing firms that embrace product innovation and product–service innovation (Bustinza *et al.*, 2018). We base this assumption on previous studies regarding human capital and innovation (Bayon *et al.*, 2016; Fonseca *et al.*, 2019; Ma *et al.*, 2019; Sun *et al.*, 2020), but also on studies that analyse the link between a firm's knowledge resources and manufacturing product/service innovativeness (Lafuente *et al.*, 2017; Lafuente *et al.*, 2019a).

Manufacturing firms are progressively innovating in services as a way to escape the commodity trap and gain competitive advantage (Bustinza *et al.*, 2019a). As such, instead of channelling their efforts into product innovation (i.e. traditional manufacturing), they increasingly focus on integrating innovative services to accompany their core products, and thus offer solutions or bundles of products and services (Vendrell-Herrero *et al.*, 2018) as a new manufacturing paradigm referred to as "product-service innovation" (Bustinza *et al.*, 2018; Bustinza *et al.*, 2019b). The main outcome of product–service innovation is the generation of additional value for customers, enabling firms to achieve greater performance gains (Vendrell-Herrero *et al.*, 2017; Bustinza *et al.*, 2018). In this study, we focus on the effect of two different types of manufacturing innovations, i.e. firms that adopt product innovation, and firms that adopt product–service innovation – and the individual effect of each of these innovation strategies on a firm's performance. To this end, we base our research on previous studies into product–service innovation and performance benefits, especially labour productivity (Opazo-Basáez *et al.*, 2018). However, considering that multiple configurations of business factors may lead to optimal results in product–service innovation (Sjödin *et al.*, 2019); this implies that it is not just a single route that can produce high performance benefits. We, therefore, do not dismiss the possible connection between a

firm's manufacturing innovation portfolio and other factors considered in this study (i.e. human capital and firm size).

Firm size has long been considered to be an important determinant of innovation activity, although this connection is far from being established (McGuirk *et al.*, 2015; Lafuente *et al.*, 2019b). Some researchers state that SMEs are more flexible and therefore better able to embrace and adjust to innovations (Chowdhury *et al.*, 2014). These arguments are mainly based on SMEs' ability to avoid bureaucratic inertia and adapt to changes on markets (Stock *et al.*, 2002). Other researchers, however, suggest that large enterprises (LEs) are in a better position to exploit innovation options, mostly because of their capacity to accumulate a larger store of knowledge resources and capabilities (Bustinza *et al.*, 2019c). Overall, such controversial evidence shows that the debate between firm size and innovation capability is far from over, but also indicates that, to a considerable extent, size can have an effect on performance benefits in innovative firms. We base this argument on previous studies regarding firm size and performance outcomes (Hashi and Stojcic, 2013). Therefore, this study argues that firm size, which is widely considered in literature as being a differentiating factor for innovation capacity, may affect the performance outcomes of manufacturing firms that embrace innovation strategies – for the purpose of our study, this means product and product–service innovation.

2.1 Research hypotheses

2.1.1 Human capital composition. Innovation in organisations is, first and foremost, a human issue (Kianto *et al.*, 2017). Therefore, human capital has been widely considered as an important resource in determining innovation success (Ma *et al.*, 2019; Sun *et al.*, 2020), and has a direct effect on value added as an input, either through higher direct productivity or better decision-making (Ballot *et al.*, 2001). Thus, it has been recognised as an important source of competitive advantage for firms (Barney and Wright, 1998) and, consequently, the literature has largely focused on the role of human capital as a key resource for a firm's performance benefits (Buller and McEvoy, 2012; Chowhan, 2016), as well as on the relationship these benefits have with the level of education attained by their workers (McGuirk *et al.*, 2015). Workers' level of education largely determines the innovation benefits of an organisation; an assertion that has also been confirmed with regard to performance benefits Millan *et al.* (2014). As such, existing evidence substantiates the fact that human capital (as the internal composition of knowledge resource) plays a key role in determining organisational performance (Yang and Lin, 2009), business performance (Kim *et al.*, 2012) and financial returns (Chu *et al.*, 2006). Overall these findings confirm the importance of human capital as being conducive towards performance benefits and enable us to posit the following hypotheses:

- H1. Human capital composition has a positive effect on labour productivity.
- H1a. High-level education has a positive effect on labour productivity.
- H1b. Medium-high level education has a positive effect on labour productivity.
- H1c. Medium-low level education has a positive effect on labour productivity.

2.1.2 Manufacturing innovation portfolio. As firms possess heterogeneous innovative resources, they adopt different innovation paths to configure their innovation portfolio (Ismail, 2018). Primarily, this portfolio can be based on four innovation strategies, namely, product innovation, process innovation, marketing innovation and organisational innovation (Camison and Villar-López, 2014). Moreover, extant research has introduced

product–service innovation and innovative manufacturing technologies as additional innovation catalysts (Bustinza *et al.*, 2018) regardless of peer relevance, and considering the purpose of this study, we can affirm that product innovation and product–service innovation are of great importance in creating the innovation portfolio of innovative manufacturing companies (Bustinza *et al.*, 2019a; Bustinza *et al.*, 2019b). Within the current manufacturing scenario, product innovation has been recognised as a mechanism to respond to consumer needs (i.e. in the form of new product offerings), and thus as an important innovation-type in achieving greater performance from different perspectives such as organisational (Gunday *et al.*, 2011), financial (Dunk, 2011) and operational (Jacobs and Swink, 2011).

On the other hand, through services based on high value-added relationships with customers, product–service innovation has been widely promoted as a crucial strategy to achieve differentiation over competitors, and thereby increase the competitive advantage of the company and greater financial (Ambroise *et al.*, 2018), operational (Opazo-Basáez *et al.*, 2018) and strategic performance (Wang *et al.*, 2018). Taken together, this confirms the significance of innovation strategy adoption (i.e. innovation portfolio) on performance benefits and enables us to state the following hypotheses:

- H2.* The innovation portfolio has a positive effect on the relationship between human capital composition and labour productivity.
- H2a.* Product innovation has a positive effect on the relationship between human capital composition and labour productivity.
- H2b.* Product–service innovation has a positive effect on the relationship between human capital composition and labour productivity.

2.1.3 Firm size. Firm size is related to the capabilities and resources available for innovation, including technical, human and financial resources. Therefore, firm size is considered to be an important factor in fostering innovative success (Stock *et al.*, 2002). In this regard, literature suggests that SMEs have a greater potential to promote collaboration and cooperation among workers and require less effort to accept and start innovation activities (Leal-Rodríguez *et al.*, 2015). These characteristics encourage creative thinking and commitment, and also enhance the innovation performance of the firm. Conversely, several studies highlight the fact that LEs have more opportunities to capitalize on a firm’s capacity and resources with a view to investing in R&D and innovation (Leal-Rodríguez *et al.*, 2015). Thus, an LE will have the ability to employ more R&D staff, which will reverberate on economies of scale in R&D, and consequently on the firm’s innovation performance (Stock *et al.*, 2002). Nevertheless, despite the discrepancies, there is significant evidence to suggest the existence of a positive relationship between firm size and performance outcomes in innovative manufacturing firms (Hashi and Stojcic, 2013). 2013; Forés and Camisón, 2016). However, we posit that the effect of one size or another might depend—among other things

—on the configuration of the firm’s innovation portfolio and human capital (i.e. knowledge resources). Accordingly, we present the following hypotheses:

- H3.* Firm size has a positive effect on the relationship between human capital composition and labour productivity.
- H3a.* Medium-sized enterprises (SMEs) have a positive effect on the relationship between human capital composition and labour productivity.

H3b. LEs have a positive effect on the relationship between human capital composition and labour productivity.

Figure 1 presents the hypotheses formulated in a theoretical model. The next section addresses the study methodology.

3. Data collection and methodology

3.1 Data description

The data was obtained from the ENIIM [1]. For its part, the ENIIM data is collected by the Peruvian Institute of Statistics and Informatics every three years, it follows the methodology of the Oslo Manual [2] for international comparisons and uses the Central Directory of Companies and Establishments as a source. The ENIIM uses stratified random sampling by location, size, industry and other country-specific information. The first survey was carried out in 2012 and covered the period from 2009 to 2011, while the second survey was carried out in 2015 and covered the period from 2012 to 2014. The ENIIM has been used in previous studies on management issues and published in international journals; see, for example, Heredia-Pérez *et al.* (2019), Arenas and Gonzalez (2019) and Del Carpio-Gallegos and Miralles-Torner (2018).

Our study uses information available from the ENIIM database conducted in 2015. The final sample of this survey consists of 1,452 manufacturing firms. The sample size was obtained from the total population of 161,887 manufacturing companies in Peru (INEI, 2017). For its part, the information was collected through direct face-to-face surveys, which entailed completing an electronic questionnaire using a tablet device, with 52 questions geared to obtaining information about the innovation processes and the business environment of manufacturing firms. This involved the participation of an official qualified pollster and informants were the firm's managers or owners who participated in the company's decision-making. In accordance with our research objectives (to know whether

Figure 1.
Theoretical model

human capital composition affects labour productivity of manufacturing firms) and to select the sample, we focused on Chapter VII of the ENIIM that deals with innovation outcome [3].

Thus, to understand the specific nuances of various innovation outcomes, the study focused only on companies that are engaged in product innovation and service innovation. For instance, the survey includes the following questions:

- Q1. During the 2012–2014 period, in relation to product innovations, did the company manage to introduce a new or significantly improved product to the market?
- Q2. During the 2012–2014 period, in relation to service innovations, did the company manage to introduce a new or significantly improved service to the market?

As such, we consider product innovators to be those companies who responded positively to the introduction of product innovations, but negatively to service innovations. Likewise, we consider product–service innovators to be those companies that responded positively to the introduction of both product and service innovations. Using these criteria, we included 584 companies in total, and Table 1 summarises the composition of the sample.

3.2 Description of variables

The dependent variable – labour productivity – is calculated as the ratio of total sales per worker. This measure aims to proxy firm efficiency by using production inputs, thereby providing a basis for comparing performance across manufacturing firms (Grazzi *et al.*, 2016). The independent variables comprise human capital (workers with technical,

Industry/size	SMEs	LEs	Total
Food products processing	12.64	20.00	17.81
Beverage manufacturing	1.15	2.68	2.23
Manufacture of textile products	5.17	5.37	5.31
Garment manufacturing	3.45	5.37	4.79
Manufacture of leather products and related products	5.75	1.22	2.57
Wood production and manufacture of wood and cork products	1.72	1.71	1.71
Manufacture of paper and related products	0.57	3.17	2.40
Printing and playback of recordings	0.57	1.22	1.03
Manufacture of coke and petroleum refining products	0.00	0.49	0.34
Manufacture of chemical substances and products	6.90	8.29	7.88
Manufacture of pharmaceutical products, medicinal chemicals	4.02	2.93	3.25
Manufacture of rubber and plastic products	8.05	10.00	9.42
Manufacture of other non-metallic mineral products	21.26	22.68	22.26
Manufacture of common metals	1.15	1.22	1.20
Manufacture of fabricated metal products, except machinery	5.75	4.15	4.62
Manufacture of computer products, electronics and optics	0.57	0.00	0.17
Electrical equipment manufacturing	4.02	2.44	2.91
Manufacture of machinery and equipment	5.17	2.44	3.25
Manufacture of motor vehicles, trailers and semi-trailers	5.17	1.22	2.40
Manufacture of other transport equipment	2.87	0.49	1.20
Furniture manufacturing	2.87	0.98	1.54
Other manufacturing industries	0.57	1.95	1.54
Repair and installation of machinery and equipment	0.57	0.00	0.17
<i>Total</i>	<i>100</i>	<i>100</i>	<i>100</i>

Table 1.
Sample composition
according to industry
(percentage of firms)

Source: ENIIM database (2015)

university and postgraduate studies). Table 2 shows the definitions of the variables used in this study.

On the other hand, it was important to depict how these companies differ in terms of characteristics of innovation portfolio and size. To this end, we grouped companies together according to their innovation portfolio, namely, product innovation and product–service innovation (Bustinza *et al.*, 2018). This was fundamentally because product innovation and product–service innovation are considered very important in shaping the innovation portfolio of modern manufacturing companies (Bustinza *et al.*, 2019a; Bustinza *et al.*, 2019b). In accordance with the two strategic choices presented by our study, two groups of companies were taken into account: those that were only engaged in product innovation; and those that were engaged in product–service innovation.

Furthermore, regarding size, we considered two size categories depending on the number of workers in the firm. The first category comprised enterprises with less than 50 workers (SMEs) and the second category comprised enterprises with more than 50 workers (LEs). In Tables 3 and 4, we show the statistical summary of these groups of companies with their respective results, using average difference tests.

Variable	Definition	Scales	
Labour productivity	Total sales per total permanent workers	Logarithm	Table 2. Definition of variables
High-level education	Proportion of workers with postgraduate studies	Logarithm	
Medium-high level education	Proportion of workers with universities studies	Logarithm	
Medium-low level education	Proportion of workers with technical studies	Logarithm	

Variables	(1) SMEs		(2) LEs		(3) Difference in means		Table 3. Summary of statistics for firms with product innovation
	Mean	SD	Mean	SD	Diff.	t-test	
L_Labour productivity	12.4735	1.1876	12.3536	0.91717	0.1198	0.2822	
P_High-level education	0.0496	0.1047	0.0241	0.0302	0.0254	0.0049	
P_Medium-high level education	0.1837	0.1590	0.1519	0.1336	0.0318	0.0366	
P_Medium-low level education	0.2083	0.1693	0.1962	0.1753	0.0121	0.4777	

Variables	(1) SMEs		(2) LEs		(3) Difference in means		Table 4. Summary of statistics for firms with product–service innovation
	Mean	SD	Mean	SD	Diff.	t-test	
L_Labour productivity	11.7367	1.1995	12.4045	0.9848	-0.6678	0.0087	
P_High level education	0.0385	0.0563	0.0300	0.0415	0.0085	0.4524	
P_Medium-high level Education	0.1574	0.1020	0.1732	0.1326	-0.0158	0.5122	
P_Medium-low level Education	0.2628	0.2201	0.2363	0.1820	0.0265	0.5572	

3.3 Method and regression model

In accordance with our research objectives, we estimated the effects of human capital composition on productivity in terms of innovation portfolio and company size. The descriptive data and regression models were computed using R software and to test the hypotheses, we analysed the relationship through regression models using the ordinary least squares (OLS) method. Thus, the model took the following form:

$$Productivity_i \approx a_0 + a_1 HumanCapitalComposition_i + \epsilon_i \quad (1)$$

[. . .] where the sub-index i refers to the firms. $HumanCapitalComposition_i$ is a vector of level education and ϵ_i is the error term. To support $H1$, a_1 needs to be positive:.

$$Productivity_j \approx b_0 + b_1 HumanCapitalComposition_j + \epsilon_j \quad (2)$$

$$Productivity_k \approx c_0 + c_1 HumanCapitalComposition_k + \epsilon_k \quad (3)$$

[. . .] where the sub-index j refers to the firms with product innovations and sub-index k refers to the firms with product-service innovations. $HumanCapitalComposition_{j,k}$ is a vector of level education and $\epsilon_{j,k}$ is the error term. To support $H2$, $c_1 > b_1$:

$$Productivity_l \approx d_0 + d_1 HumanCapitalComposition_l + \epsilon_l \quad (4)$$

$$Productivity_m \approx e_0 + e_1 HumanCapitalComposition_m + \epsilon_m \quad (5)$$

[. . .] where the sub-index l refers to the SMEs with product innovation and sub-index m refers to the LEs. $HumanCapitalComposition_{l,m}$ is a vector of level education and $\epsilon_{l,m}$ is the error term. To support $H3a$, $e_1 > d_1$:

$$Productivity_n \approx f_0 + f_1 HumanCapitalComposition_n + \epsilon_n \quad (6)$$

$$Productivity_o \approx g_0 + g_1 HumanCapitalComposition_o + \epsilon_o \quad (7)$$

[. . .] where the sub-index n refers to the SMEs with product-service innovations and sub-index o refers to the LEs. $HumanCapitalComposition_{n,o}$ is a vector of level education and $\epsilon_{n,o}$ is the error term. To support $H3b$, $g_1 > f_1$.

In terms of analysing the global significance of the model, we used the F-test as one more measure of goodness of fit. Furthermore, in accordance with the aims of the research at hand, we used the regression models [equations (1)–(7)] to depict how these companies differ in characteristics of innovation portfolio and size.

4. Results and discussion

The results indicate that human capital composition in manufacturing firms is a critical determinant of productivity according to their innovation portfolio and firm size. We computed productivity distributions for companies with product innovation and compared them to their counterparts with product–service innovation. This enabled us to graphically test the probability of productivity according to innovation portfolio and company size. The Kolmogorov–Smirnov test (Wilcox, 2005) provided statistical validity for the distribution

comparison, and this test can thus establish a graphical bivariate correlation between the variables of interest. For instance, as shown in Figure 2, large manufacturing firms with product innovation are more prone to productivity to a statistically significant degree. However, there are no relevant results to show that differences exist between firms that are engaged in product–service innovations and those who are engaged in product innovation, i.e. the two forms of distribution are not statistically different (at 5%, a visual interpretation of the figure thus supports partial validity of *H2*). Our evidence does not, however, support the conclusion that there are differences in productivity between firms that are engaged in product innovation and firms that are engaged in product–service innovations. Although the comparison of innovation portfolio distribution is instructive, the hypothesis must be tested through OLS regressions.

If we analyse Table 5, we can see that the equation (1) is estimated for the total sample of 584 manufacturing firms. In other words, companies that were engaged in product and product–service innovations (Model 1). Furthermore, we can see that equations (2) and (3) are estimated separately for groups of companies according to the innovation portfolio as mentioned above, namely, companies that were engaged only in product innovation (Model 2) and companies that were engaged in product–service innovation (Model 3). In addition, we can see that equations (4)–(7) were estimated separately for companies according to

Figure 2. Innovation portfolio and productivity distributions

Table 5.
Regression models

Variables	Total sample (Model 1)	Total PI (Model 2)	Total PSI (Model 3)	PISMEs (Model 4)	PI LEs (Model 5)	PSI SMEs (Model 6)	PSILEs (Model 7)
(Intercept)	11.7924*** (0.0726)	11.8121*** (0.0764)	11.6369*** (0.2142)	11.8854*** (0.1853)	11.7735*** (0.0795)	11.3949*** (0.4756)	11.7558*** (0.2235)
High-level education	3.6131*** (0.6418)	3.7022*** (0.6596)	2.7523 (2.2232)	3.4594*** (0.8902)	4.9919*** (1.6277)	-1.2077 (4.0176)	6.9629*** (2.6584)
Medium-high level education	2.3540*** (0.2825)	2.2517*** (0.2970)	2.9641*** (0.8319)	1.8039*** (0.5849)	2.4371*** (0.3648)	4.2236 (2.4819)	2.2456*** (0.8310)
Medium-low level education	0.3183 (0.2185)	0.4827** (0.2410)	-0.0843 (0.5263)	0.4086 (0.5524)	0.4560* (0.2589)	-1.0519 (1.1716)	0.2138 (0.5739)
F	41.53***	37.96***	5.405***	8.362***	32.17***	1.014	7.148***
RMSE	0.9304	0.9062	1.0275	1.1048	0.8112	1.1987	0.8787
R ²	0.1768	0.1930	0.1395	0.1529	0.2247	0.1013	0.2371
Adj. R ²	0.1726	0.1880	0.1137	0.1346	0.2177	0.0143	0.2039
Num. obs	584	480	104	143	337	31	73

Notes: *** $p < 0.01$; ** $p < 0.05$; * $p < 0.1$. PI = Product innovation; PSI = Product-service innovation

innovation portfolio and their size, namely, SMEs (Models 4 and 6) and LEs (Models 5 and 7).

Thus, Table 5 shows the results of the regressions for each of these models considered. Firstly, if we focus on the total sample (Model 1), we observe that workers with a higher-level education (coefficient = 3.6131***) and workers with medium-high level education (coefficient = 2.3540***) have a positive effect on the labour productivity of manufacturing firms. In addition, an evaluated model fit based on the model's global significance test and the root mean square error (RMSE) show the results of the data ($F = 41.53^{***}$; $RMSE = 0.9304$), being satisfactorily significant. Therefore, these results strongly support *H1a* and *H1b*, and so we can state that the highest levels of education are positively related to productivity in manufacturing firms. Furthermore, it is important to mention that these results coincide with previous studies such as those by Corvers (1997), Arvanitis and Loukis (2009) and Sun *et al.* (2020).

Secondly, as can be seen from the results according to innovation portfolio, i.e. companies that were engaged in product innovation (Model 2) and companies that were engaged in product–service innovation (Model 3), we find some differences that may be valuable in providing a better understanding of the effects of human capital composition on labour productivity in both groups of manufacturing companies. Hence, if we focus on the first group of companies (Model 2), we can appreciate that all variables have a positive effect on labour productivity, i.e. workers with a higher level of education (coefficient = 3.7022***), workers with a medium-high level of education (coefficient = 2.2517***) and also workers with a medium-low levels of education (coefficient = 0.4827**) have positive effects on the labour productivity of manufacturing firms. Meanwhile, in the second group of companies (Model 3), only workers with a medium-high level of education (coefficient = 2.9641***) have positive effects on the labour productivity of manufacturing firms. Therefore, this suggests that the innovation portfolio has a positive effect on the relationship between human capital composition and labour productivity. In addition, evaluating the model fit based on the model's global significance test and the RMSE shows the results of the data for firms from the first group ($F = 37.96^{***}$; $RMSE = 0.9062$) and for firms from the second group ($F = 5.405^{***}$; $RMSE = 1.0275$) being satisfactorily significant. Therefore, these results strongly support *H2a* and partially support *H2b* because of the fact that, at this level of analysis, manufacturing firms that are engaged in product–service innovation do not have positive effects on the relationships between all levels of human capital and productivity. One reason that could explain this result is that the proportion of highly educated workers required for companies with these characteristics (product–service innovation) is remarkably high and thus is not a differentiator. Hence, this result makes it necessary to carry out further analyses to understand the contribution of human capital on productivity. Therefore, we do not dismiss the possible connection between a firm's manufacturing innovation portfolio and other factors considered in this study, such as company size.

Thirdly, when we carried out the analysis taking into account company size, we found interesting differences. For instance, with regard to innovation portfolio, SMEs that were engaged in product innovation (Model 4) and LEs that were engaged in product innovation (Model 5), we found some differences that may be valuable in providing a better understanding of the effects of human capital composition on labour productivity according to firm size in this group of manufacturing companies. Hence, if we focus on SMEs (Model 4), we can appreciate that workers with a higher level of education (coefficient = 3.4594***) and workers with a medium-high level of education (coefficient = 1.8039***) have positive effects on labour productivity. Meanwhile, in terms of the LEs (Model 5), we can appreciate

that all variables have a positive effect on labour productivity, i.e. workers with a higher level of education (coefficient = 4.9919***), workers with a medium-high level education (coefficient = 2.4371***) and workers with a medium-low level of education (coefficient = 0.4560*) have positive effects on labour productivity. In addition, when evaluating the model fit based on the model's global significance test and the RMSE ($F = 8.362^{***}$; $RMSE = 1.1048$) for SMEs and ($F = 32.17^{***}$; $RMSE = 0.8112$) for LEs, these results show the data to be significant only for LEs that were engaged in product innovation. Therefore, these results partially support *H3a* and strongly support *H3b* and suggest that education has consistently had a positive effect on individual worker productivity, perhaps because of the latter's capacity to accumulate a larger store of knowledge resources and capabilities (Bustinza *et al.*, 2019c; Ma *et al.*, 2019; Sun *et al.*, 2020). Moreover, LEs also have more opportunities to capitalize on a firm's capacity and resources to invest in R&D and innovation (Leal-Rodríguez *et al.*, 2015). By contrast, in SMEs, workers with low levels of education are not prone to productivity, with such controversial evidence showing the ongoing debate between firm size and innovation capability (Forés and Camison, 2016).

On the other hand, if we focus on SMEs that were engaged in product–service innovation (Model 6) and LEs that were engaged in product–service innovation (Model 7), we find greater differences that may be valuable in providing a better understanding of the effects of human capital composition on labour productivity according to firm size in this group of manufacturing companies. Therefore, if we focus on SMEs (Model 6), we can see that none of the variables, i.e. workers' level of education has positive effects on productivity. Meanwhile, in LEs (Model 7), we can appreciate that workers with a higher level of education (coefficient = 6.9629***) and workers with a medium-high level of education (coefficient = 2.2456***) have positive effects on labour productivity. In addition, these results were corroborated when we evaluated the model fit based on the model's global significance test and the RMSE ($F = 1.014$; $RMSE = 1.1987$) for SMEs, and ($F = 7.148^{***}$; $RMSE = 0.8787$) for LEs. These results showed significant data only for LEs that were engaged in product–service innovation. Therefore, these results do not support *H3a* and strongly support *H3b* and suggest that adding value to product innovation through service innovation (product–service innovation) requires high levels of education (Bustinza *et al.*, 2018; Bustinza *et al.*, 2019c; Opazo-Basaez *et al.*, 2019). Moreover, LEs also have more opportunities to capitalize on a firm's capacity and resources to invest in R&D and innovation (Leal-Rodríguez *et al.*, 2015). Hence, this evidence suggests the existence of a positive relationship between firm size and performance in innovative manufacturing firms ((Hashi and Stojcic, 2013; Forés and Camison, 2016; Bustinza *et al.*, 2019c). In this sense, our study contributes to the controversy that still exists regarding firm size and innovation capability (McGuirk *et al.*, 2015; Lafuente *et al.*, 2019b).

Lastly, if we compared LEs that were engaged in product innovation (Model 5) and LEs with product–service innovation (Model 7), we find no greater differences in a broad sense, although when a level of significance was observed in each variables, the results suggest that LEs with product–service innovation have a more significant relationship between human capital and labour productivity than LEs with product innovations. In any case, all evidence shows that there is a positive relationship between human capital composition and labour productivity in manufacturing firms. Moreover, there are differences between manufacturing companies according to human capital composition, innovation portfolio and company size.

5. Conclusions, limitations and future research

5.1 Theoretical implications

This article not only contributes to the RBV theory by reinforcing the arguments that widely indicate that human capital is considered an important resource for the competitive advantage of companies (Barney and Wright, 1998; Wright *et al.*, 2001) that can affect the labour productivity of manufacturing companies (Corvers, 1997; Arvanitis and Loukis, 2009) but also that this relationship may be different depending on the type of innovation pursued by the company and its size.

From a theoretical standpoint, all this evidence shows that there is a positive relationship between human capital composition and labour productivity in manufacturing firms. Therefore, the resource-based theoretical perspective provides a rationale for the link between human capital and performance in innovative such firms (Sun *et al.*, 2020). Specifically, our results show that workers' level of education influences the innovation performance of firms regarding innovation portfolio (Lafuente *et al.*, 2017; Vendrell-Herrero *et al.*, 2017; Bustinza *et al.*, 2018; Bustinza *et al.*, 2019a; Bustinza *et al.*, 2019b; Lafuente *et al.*, 2019a). In addition, the results show that there are differences between SMEs and LEs, the latter being those evidencing greater performance. Thus, the study adds arguments to the debate that has emerged around whether firm size is an important determinant of innovation activity (Lafuente *et al.*, 2019b).

Lastly, our results tested these existing theories originating from the USA and Europe (Aguinis *et al.*, 2020) in the Peruvian manufacturing context. The empirical analysis is based on a sample of 584 Peruvian manufacturing firms and illustrates the fact that the greatest challenges these companies face entails increasing the productivity of their workforces, as the firms' demand for skills is associated with innovation (González-Velosa *et al.*, 2016); in particular, the lack of skilled labour is a constraint to innovation in SMEs (Feldens *et al.*, 2012).

5.2 Managerial and policy implications

This study contains two main implications; first, our findings suggest that a firm's highly educated human capital results in greater probability of labour productivity. Hence, as human resource management is a dynamic and complex process (Barney and Wright, 1998), this requires suitable strengthening of workers' innovation capacities (Fonseca *et al.*, 2019). As such, an appropriate mix of human resource management (Chowhan, 2016) with innovation management (Seclen-Luna and López-Valladares, 2020) is required, as both processes are keys to achieving high levels of productivity and competitiveness (Barney and Wright, 1998; Wright *et al.*, 2001; Lafuente and Rabetino, 2011; Chowdhury *et al.*, 2014).

The second implication suggests that it is important for regional governments to play a crucial role as facilitators when considering integrating links between manufacturing firms (especially SMEs) and external actors (e.g. universities), and when designing science, technology and innovation policies (Seclen-Luna *et al.*, 2020). Specifically, results call for the development of strategic partnerships with educational establishments, thus boosting training and education for product–service innovation settings (as demonstrated in *H3a* and *H3b*). Hence, these challenges require effective talent management to ensure appropriate access to qualified talent. In this regard, organisations must conceive education as being a strategic mechanism for addressing pivotal talent shortages (Opazo-Basaez *et al.*, 2019).

Lastly, assessment of the effects of human capital composition, innovation portfolio and business size is not only relevant because it is positively related to labour productivity, but because it can support business managers in their quest to better design their innovation portfolio (Bustinza *et al.*, 2019a; Bustinza *et al.*, 2019b). Thus, our contextual results have the potential to influence managerial and political agendas in developing contexts, such as Peru.

5.3 Limitations and future research

Although these results are useful for their implications for business managers and policymakers, as they advance knowledge about the relationships between human capital and productivity in manufacturing firms, this study has limitations that suggest the need for future research. Firstly, notwithstanding the fact the empirical analysis is reliably supported by the ENIIM database, the low number of observations for some of the key variables prohibits analysis at an industry level. Furthermore, firms might be competing for the same resources in their competitive environment with similar informational and institutional barriers, allowing only for interpretations at the level of manufacturers as a whole, and so this factor remains open for future research. In the same vein, at a micro level, our study does not evaluate how manufacturing firms manage their human resources; further research on this issue would therefore also be valuable.

Secondly, the analysis carried out in this study is of a cross-cutting nature, and so it does not capture all the dynamics of innovation and the allocation of resources and capacities in companies. Furthermore, despite the relationships which are significant in our models, other factors not included in the current models may also play an important role. Thus, future research will need to corroborate the results in specific contexts in a long-term analysis, so as to determine some of the causal mechanisms. Lastly, it would also be very worthwhile to carry out comparative studies among different developing regions/countries, which would help governments to improve their design of science, technology and innovation policies.

Notes

1. The ENIIM is available at <http://iinei.inei.gob.pe/microdatos/>
2. The Oslo Manual "Guidelines for Collecting, Reporting and Using Data on Innovation" can be found at: www.oecd.org/science/oslo-manual-2018-9789264304604-en.htm
3. The survey questionnaire can be accessed via: <http://iinei.inei.gob.pe/microdatos/>

References

- Aguinis, H. and Joo, H. (2014), "Research on Hispanics benefits the field of management", *Journal of Managerial Psychology*, Vol. 29 No. 6, pp. 604-615.
- Aguinis, H., Lazzarini, S., Vassolo, R., Amorós, J.E. and Allen, D.G. (2020), "Conducting management research in Latin America: why and what's in it for you?", *Journal of Management*, Vol. 46 No. 5, pp. 615-636.
- Amabile, T.M. (1988), "A model of creativity and innovation in organizations", *Research in Organizational Behaviour*, No. 10, pp. 123-167.
- Ambroise, L., Prim-Allaz, I. and Teyssier, C. (2018), "Financial performance of servitized manufacturing firms: a configuration issue between servitization strategies and customer-oriented organizational design", *Industrial Marketing Management*, Vol. 71 No. 71, pp. 54-68.
- Arenas, J.J. and Gonzalez, D. (2019), "Collaboration for R&D projects between the industry and external agents: evidence from manufacturing companies in Peru", *Latin American Business Review*, Vol. 20 No. 1, pp. 37-60.
- Arvanitis, S. and Loukis, E.N. (2009), "Information and communication technologies, human capital, workplace organization and labour productivity: a comparative study based on firm-level data for Greece and Switzerland", *Information Economics and Policy*, Vol. 21 No. 1, pp. 43-61.
- Audretsch, D., Coad, A. and Segarra, A. (2014), "Firm growth and innovation", *Small Business Economics*, Vol. 43 No. 4, pp. 743-749.

-
- Ballot, G., Fakhfakh, F. and Taymaz, E. (2001), "Firms' human capital, R&D and performance: a study on French and Swedish firms", *Labour Economics*, Vol. 8 No. 4, pp. 443-462.
- Barney, J.B. and Wright, P.M. (1998), "On becoming a strategic partner: the role of human resources in gaining competitive advantage", *Human Resource Management*, Vol. 37 No. 1, pp. 31-46.
- Bayon, M.C., Lafuente, E. and Vaillant, Y. (2016), "Human capital and the decision to exploit innovative opportunity", *Management Decision*, Vol. 54 No. 7, pp. 1615-1632.
- Buller, P. and McEvoy, G. (2012), "Strategy, human resource management and performance: sharpening line of sight", *Human Resource Management Review*, Vol. 22 No. 1, pp. 43-56.
- Bustinza, O.F., Vendrell-Herrero, F. and Gomes, E. (2019c), "Unpacking the effect of strategic ambidexterity on performance: a cross-country comparison of MMNEs developing product-service innovation", *International Business Review*, in Press.
- Bustinza, O.F., Vendrell-Herrero, F. and Baines, T. (2017), "Service implementation in manufacturing: an organisational transformation perspective", *International Journal of Production Economics*, Vol. 192, pp. 1-8.
- Bustinza, O.F., Lafuente, E., Rabetino, R., Vaillant, Y. and Vendrell-Herrero, F. (2019a), "Make-or-buy configurational approaches in product-service ecosystems and performance", *Journal of Business Research*, Vol. 104, pp. 393-401.
- Bustinza, O.F., Gomes, E., Vendrell-Herrero, F. and Baines, T. (2019b), "Product-service innovation and performance: the role of collaborative partnerships and R&D intensity", *R&D Management*, Vol. 49 No. 1, pp. 33-45.
- Bustinza, O.F., Vendrell-Herrero, F., Gomes, E., Lafuente, E., Opazo-Basáez, M. and Rabetino, R. (2018), "Product-service innovation and performance: unveiling the complexities", *International Journal of Business Environment*, Vol. 10 No. 2, pp. 95-111.
- Camison, C. and Villar-López, A. (2014), "Organizational innovation as an enabler of technological innovation capabilities and firm performance", *Journal of Business Research*, Vol. 67 No. 1, pp. 2891-2902.
- Chowdhury, S., Schulz, E., Milner, M. and Van De Voort, D. (2014), "Core employee based human capital and revenue productivity in small firms: an empirical investigation", *Journal of Business Research*, Vol. 67 No. 11, pp. 2473-2479.
- Chowhan, J. (2016), "Unpacking the black box: understanding the relationship between strategy, HRM practices, innovation and organizational performance", *Human Resource Management Journal*, Vol. 26 No. 2, pp. 112-133.
- Chu, P.Y., Lin, Y.L., Hsiung, H.H. and Liu, T.Y. (2006), "Intellectual capital: an empirical study of ITRI", *Technological Forecasting and Social Change*, Vol. 73 No. 7, pp. 886-902.
- Cohen, W.M. and Levinthal, D.A. (1990), "Absorptive capacity: a new perspective on learning and innovation", *Administrative Science Quarterly*, Vol. 35 No. 1, pp. 128-152.
- Coronado, D., Acosta, M. and Fernandez, A. (2008), "Attitudes to innovation in peripheral economic regions", *Research Policy*, Vol. 37 Nos 6/7, pp. 1009-1021.
- Corvers, F. (1997), "The impact of human capital on labour productivity in manufacturing sectors of the European Union", *Applied Economics*, Vol. 29 No. 8, pp. 975-987.
- Cuervo-Cazurra, A. (2016), "Multi Latinas as sources of new research insights: the learning and escape drivers of international expansion", *Journal of Business Research*, Vol. 69 No. 6, pp. 1963-1972.
- Cuervo-Cazurra, A. and Dau, L.A. (2009), "Promarket reforms and firm profitability in developing countries", *Academy of Management Journal*, Vol. 52 No. 6, pp. 1348-1368.
- Del Carpio-Gallegos, J.F. and Miralles-Torner, F. (2018), "Absorptive capacity and innovation in low-tech companies in emerging economies", *Journal of Technology Management and Innovation*, Vol. 13 No. 2, pp. 3-10.
- Dunk, A.S. (2011), "Product innovation, budgetary control, and the financial performance of firms", *The British Accounting Review*, Vol. 43 No. 2, pp. 102-111.

-
- Feldens, M., Maccari, E. and Garcez, M. (2012), "Barriers for production innovation in small and medium technology-based firms in Brazil", *Brazilian Business Review*, Vol. 9 No. 3, pp. 1-22.
- Fonseca, T., De Faria, P. and Lima, F. (2019), "Human capital and innovation: the importance of the optimal organizational task structure", *Research Policy*, Vol. 48 No. 3, pp. 616-627.
- Forés, B. and Camisón, C. (2016), "Does incremental and radical innovation performance depend on different types of knowledge accumulation capabilities and organizational size?", *Journal of Business Research*, Vol. 69 No. 2, pp. 831-848.
- González-Velosa, C., Rosas, D. and Flores, R. (2016), "On-the-job training in Latin America and the Caribbean: recent evidence", in Grazzi, M. and Pietrobelli, C. (Eds), *Firm Innovation and Productivity in Latin America and the Caribbean. The Engine of Economic Development*, IDB and Palgrave Macmillan, New York, NY, pp. 137-166.
- Grazzi, M., Pietrobelli, C. and Szirmai, A. (2016), "Determinants of enterprise performance in Latin America and the Caribbean: what does the micro-evidence tell us?", In Grazzi, M. and Pietrobelli, C. (Eds), *Firm Innovation and Productivity in Latin America and the Caribbean. The Engine of Economic Development*, IDB and Palgrave Macmillan, New York, NY, pp. 1-36.
- Gunday, G., Ulusoy, G., Kilic, K. and Alpkan, L. (2011), "Effects of innovation types on firm performance", *International Journal of Production Economics*, Vol. 133 No. 2, pp. 662-676.
- Hashi, I. and Stojic, N. (2013), "The impact of innovation activities on firm performance using a multi-stage model: evidence from the community innovation survey 4", *Research Policy*, Vol. 42 No. 2, pp. 353-366.
- Heredia-Pérez, J.A., Geldes, C., Kunc, M.H. and Flores, A. (2019), "New approach to the innovation process in emerging economies: the manufacturing sector case in Chile and Peru", *Technovation*, Vol. 79, pp. 35-55.
- Hewitt-Dundas, N. (2006), "Resource and capability constraints to innovation in small and large plants", *Small Business Economics*, Vol. 26 No. 3, pp. 257-277.
- INEI (2017), *Perú: Encuesta Nacional de Innovación en la Industria Manufacturera 2015. Principales Resultados*, Instituto Nacional de Estadística e Informática, Lima.
- Ismail, R. (2018), "The impact of human capital and innovation on labour productivity of Malaysian small and medium enterprises", *International Journal of Productivity and Quality Management*, Vol. 25 No. 2, pp. 245-261.
- Jacobs, M.A. and Swink, M. (2011), "Product portfolio architectural complexity and operational performance: incorporating the roles of learning and fixed assets", *Journal of Operations Management*, Vol. 29 Nos 7/8, pp. 677-691.
- Kianto, A., Sáenz, J. and Aramburu, N. (2017), "Knowledge-based human resource management practices, intellectual capital and innovation", *Journal of Business Research*, Vol. 81, pp. 11-20.
- Kim, T., Kim, W.G., Park, S.S.S., Lee, G. and Jee, B. (2012), "Intellectual capital and business performance: what structural relationships do they have in upper-upscale hotels?", *International Journal of Tourism Research*, Vol. 14 No. 4, pp. 391-408.
- Lafuente, E., Vaillant, Y. and Vendrell-Herrero, F. (2019a), "Territorial servitization and the manufacturing renaissance in knowledge-based economies", *Regional Studies*, Vol. 53 No. 3, pp. 313-319.
- Lafuente, E., Leiva, J., Moreno, J. and Szerb, L. (2019b), "A non-parametric analysis of competitiveness efficiency: the relevance of firm size and the configuration of competitive pillars", *BRQ Business Research Quarterly*, Vol. 121, pp. 1-14.
- Lafuente, E. and Rabetino, R. (2011), "Human capital and growth in Romanian small firms", *Journal of Small Business and Enterprise Development*, Vol. 18 No. 1, pp. 74-96.
- Lafuente, E., Vaillant, Y. and Vendrell-Herrero, F. (2017), "Territorial servitization: exploring the virtuous circle connecting knowledge-intensive services and new manufacturing businesses", *International Journal of Production Economics*, Vol. 192, pp. 19-28.

-
- Leal-Rodríguez, A.L., Eldridge, S., Roldán, J.L., Leal-Millán, A.G. and Ortega-Gutiérrez, J. (2015), "Organizational unlearning, innovation outcomes, and performance: the moderating effect of firm size", *Journal of Business Research*, Vol. 68 No. 4, pp. 803-809.
- Lin, C., Lin, P., Song, F.M. and Li, C. (2011), "Managerial incentives, CEO characteristics and corporate innovation in China's private sector", *Journal of Comparative Economics*, Vol. 39 No. 2, pp. 176-190.
- Lin, Y. and Wu, L.Y. (2014), "Exploring the role of dynamic capabilities in firm performance under the resource-based view framework", *Journal of Business Research*, Vol. 67 No. 3, pp. 407-413.
- McGuirk, H. and Jordan, D. (2012), "Local labour market diversity and business innovation: evidence from Irish manufacturing businesses", *European Planning Studies*, Vol. 20 No. 12, pp. 1945-1960.
- McGuirk, H., Lenihan, H. and Hart, M. (2015), "Measuring the impact of innovative human capital on small firms' propensity to innovate", *Research Policy*, Vol. 44 No. 4, pp. 965-976.
- Ma, L., Zhai, X., Zhong, W. and Zhang, Z.X. (2019), "Deploying human capital for innovation: a study of multi-country manufacturing firms", *International Journal of Production Economics*, Vol. 208, pp. 241-253.
- Millan, J.M., Congregado, E., Roman, C., Van Praag, M. and Van Stel, A. (2014), "The value of an educated population for an individual's entrepreneurship success", *Journal of Business Venturing*, Vol. 29 No. 5, pp. 612-632.
- MINTRA (2017), *Anuario Estadístico Sectorial 2016*, Ministerio del Trabajo y Promoción del Empleo, Perú, p. 390.
- Newbert, S. (2008), "Value, rareness, competitive advantage, and performance: a conceptual-level empirical investigation of the resource-based view of the firm", *Strategic Management Journal*, Vol. 29 No. 7, pp. 745-768.
- Nicholls-Nixon, C.L., Davila Castilla, J.A., Sanchez Garcia, J. and Rivera Pesquera, M. (2011), "Latin America management research: review, synthesis, and extension", *Journal of Management*, Vol. 37 No. 4, pp. 1178-1227.
- Opazo-Basáez, M., Vendrell-Herrero, F. and Bustinza, O.F. (2018), "Uncovering productivity gains of digital and green servitization: implications from the automotive industry", *Sustainability*, Vol. 10 No. 5, pp. 1-17.
- Opazo-Basaez, M., Vendrell-Herrero, F. and Bustinza, O.F. (2019), "Talent for services: how gaining access to talent enables successful servitization", in Liu, Y. (Ed.), *Research Handbook of International Talent Management*, Edward Elgar Publishing, Cheltenham, pp. 35-59.
- Reyes, A.B., Newburry, W., Carneiro, J. and Cordova, C. (2019), "Using Latin America as a research laboratory. The moderating effect of trade openness on the relationship between inward and outward FD", *Multinational Business Review*, Vol. 27 No. 2, pp. 122-140.
- RICYT (2017), "Indicadores Comparativos de Ciencia y Tecnología", Red de Indicadores de Ciencia y Tecnología Iberoamericana e Interamericana (RECYT), available at: http://dev.ricyt.org/ui/v3/comparative.html?Indicator=GAS_IMD_USDxH (October 2017).
- Roxas, B., Chadee, D., de Jesus, R.M.C. and Cosape, A. (2017), "Human and social capital and environmental management in small firms: a developing country perspective", *Asian Journal of Business Ethics*, Vol. 6 No. 1, pp. 1-20.
- Seclen-Luna, J.P. and López-Valladares, H. (2020), "Influence of the use of tools for managing the early stage of product innovation process", *Innovar*, Vol. 30 No. 76, pp. 119-130.
- Seclen-Luna, J.P., Ponce-Regalado, F. and Córdova-Espinoza, M. (2020), "Exploring enablers factors to innovation outcomes. An analysis of firm level", *Revista AD-Minister*, No. 36, pp. 97-112.
- Sjödin, D., Parida, V. and Kohtamäki, M. (2019), "Relational governance strategies for advanced service provision: multiple paths to superior financial performance in servitization", *Journal of Business Research*, Vol. 101, pp. 906-915.

-
- Sorenson, O. and Fleming, L. (2004), "Science and the diffusion of knowledge", *Research Policy*, Vol. 33 No. 10, pp. 1615-1634.
- Stock, G.N., Greis, N.P. and Fischer, W.A. (2002), "Firm size and dynamic technological innovation", *Technovation*, Vol. 22 No. 9, pp. 537-549.
- Subramaniam, M. and Youndt, M.A. (2005), "The influence of intellectual capital on the types of innovative capabilities", *Academy of Management Journal*, Vol. 48 No. 3, pp. 450-463.
- Sun, X., Li, H. and Ghosal, V. (2020), "Firm-level human capital and innovation: evidence from China", *China Economic Review*, Vol. 59, p. 101388, doi: 10.1016/j.chieco.2019.101388.
- Vassolo, R.S., De Castro, J.O. and Gomez-Mejia, L. (2011), "Managing in Latin America: common issues and are search agenda", *Academy of Management Perspectives*, Vol. 25 No. 4, pp. 22-36.
- Vendrell-Herrero, F. and Bustinza, O.F. (2020), "Servitization in Europe", in De Propris, L. and Bailey, D. (Eds), *Industry 4.0 and Regional Transformations*, Routledge, London, pp. 24-41.
- Vendrell-Herrero, F., Bustinza, O.F. and Opazo-Basaez, M. (2020), "Information technologies and product-service innovation: the moderating role of service R&D team structure", *Journal of Business Research*, in press, doi: 10.1016/j.jbusres.2020.01.047.
- Vendrell-Herrero, F., Bustinza, O.F., Parry, G. and Georgantzis, N. (2017), "Servitization, digitization and supply chain interdependency", *Industrial Marketing Management*, Vol. 60, pp. 69-81.
- Vendrell-Herrero, F., Gomes, E., Bustinza, O.F. and Mellahi, K. (2018), "Uncovering the role of cross-border strategic alliances and expertise decision centralization in enhancing product-service innovation in MMNEs", *International Business Review*, Vol. 27 No. 4, pp. 814-825.
- Wang, W., Lai, K.-H. and Shou, Y. (2018), "The impact of servitization on firm performance: a meta-analysis", *International Journal of Operations and Production Management*, Vol. 38 No. 7, pp. 1562-1588.
- Wilcox, R.R. (2005), "Robust testing procedures", in Everitt, B.S. and Howell, D.C. (Eds), *Encyclopedia of Statistics in Behavioral Science*, John Wiley & Sons, Chichester, UK, pp. 1769-1770.
- World Bank (2015), *Doing Business 2015. Going beyond Efficiency*, World Bank.
- World Bank (2017), "World bank open data", available at: <http://data.worldbank.org> (October 2017).
- Wright, P.M., Dunford, B.B. and Snell, S.A. (2001), "Human resources and the resource based view of the firm", *Journal of Management*, Vol. 27 No. 6, pp. 701-721.
- Yang, C.C. and Lin, C.Y.Y. (2009), "Does intellectual capital mediate the relationship between HRM and organizational performance? Perspective of a healthcare industry in Taiwan", *The International Journal of Human Resource Management*, Vol. 20 No. 9, pp. 1965-1984.

Further reading

- Ciriaci, D., Montesor, S. and Palma, D. (2015), "Do KIBS make manufacturing more innovative? An empirical investigation of four European countries", *Technological Forecasting and Social Change*, Vol. 95, pp. 135-151.
- Lafuente, E., Vaillant, Y. and Leiva, J.C. (2018), "Sustainable and traditional product innovation without scale and experience, but only for KIBS!", *Sustainability*, Vol. 10 No. 4, p. 1169.